

USE OF INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATION QUALITY

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Annotation: The article briefly analyses the structure, experience and modern educational Programs of the advanced foreign education system such as Japan, Germany, France, USA. Moreover, achievements in the education system, educational standards are monitored. The achievements of Uzbekistan at the same time are recognized.

Keywords: country, education, experience, foreign experience, educationstructure, international evaluation.

The education of our country has experienced and is undergoing a complex process of comprehensive reforms and reconstruction. Their goal is to democratize school activities, to develop humanitarian principles, and on the basis of this, to comprehensively update and further improve the content of educational work, its form and style. Renewed education means a new way of thinking in the full sense, a healthy mind. At the present time, it is necessary to have initiative, selflessness and business acumen in the performers of unning, equal to the value, reputation and influence of education.

Success in education is mostly on the side of those who act boldly. Bold action is due to courage. School can give knowledge and enlightenment to a person, as stated by Abdulla Avloni, a classic representative of Uzbek national pedagogy.

We have always valued learning. Knowledgeable people were in the country. That is why it is our highest human duty to acquire knowledge and use the acquired knowledge for the service of our country. One of the important conditions for successfully solving these tasks is to study the experiences of foreign schools and pedagogy.

By carefully and diligently studying the international experiences, we will get rid of the work forms and methods that have become frozen in education and are losing their relevance, and we will have additional rich resources for updating it in a proper way.

The head of our state said that there is a personnel problem in the country, and all fields need modern experts who are compatible with the pace of reforms.

For this purpose, the entire education system is being improved. The development of pre-school education is a good foundation for school lessons. The quality of general secondary education is being improved based on advanced international experience and contemporary requirements. [1-3]

Modern and innovative educational institutions such as presidential schools, specialized schools named after our great scholars, creative schools, Temurbek schools were established. The fact that they have established international experiences indicates that mature personnel will be produced in the future. On November 26, 2019, the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to establish modern schools" was adopted. According to

the decision, at least 3% of schools by 2021, 20% by 2025, and 50% by 2030 the main parameters of turning percent into "modern schools" were defined.

In January of this year, the president of the Oliy Majlis, in his address to the Oliy Majlis, emphasized the need to improve school curricula based on advanced foreign experience, revise the curriculum and subjects, adapt them to international standards, and improve the quality of textbooks and literature. . He defined the tasks of improving material and technical support in schools, applying international modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

In our country, only 10% of mathematics, chemistry, physics, and biology lessons are devoted to practical training. In developed countries, this figure is 30-50 percent.

Therefore, the Ministry of Public Education has been assigned the task of wide use of digital technologies in educational programs and increasing the scope of practical training in specific subjects.

Today, the level of development of any nation's state and society, first of all, the attention it pays to human capital and human development is measured by its efforts in this direction. Today, attention to the content of education is reaching the conditions of developed countries... As a proof of this, we will analyze the education system of foreign countries. [3-5] Japanese education system.

There is no concept of "gifted student" in Japanese education. Because every student has a special talent. Among advanced countries, Japan's unique direction of education occupies a leading position. In particular, the structure of the Japanese education system is as follows: preschool education, primary school, junior high school, senior high school, higher educational institutions included in the family education system.

In primary school, teachers teach children to criticize, that is, to criticize the bad aspects of their behavior and shortcomings in school. It is clear from this that the teacher is not limited to teaching, but affects the child's all-round development.

Japan is the only developed country where the teacher's salary is higher than that of the heads of state.

Compulsory educational environment. This level of education includes children from 6 to 15 years old. Financial assistance is provided to children of needy families.

Upper secondary school includes grades 10-11-12, such schools have full-time, part-time, and evening sections.

In upper secondary schools, students pass 80 tests during the entire educational process. In addition to compulsory basic subjects, students are involved in English language, technical education and special tests according to their wishes.

Students of high and secondary school or 12-year regular school are admitted to the university. Admission to universities is divided into 2 stages: the 1st stage is held at the residence, for which tests are conducted on Japanese language, mathematics, physics, chemistry, social studies, and history.

In Japan, higher education is compulsory and it is inextricably linked with vocational education. In Japan, the role and responsibility of mothers in raising children is especially great. They consider themselves responsible to the family dynasty and the state for their children to grow up smart, wise and hardworking.

In Japan, many methodical manuals and recommendations on family education are published, many pedagogical tips are given on radio and television. Home desks in Japanese families are

remarkable. It is a perfect, side-protected device, a bookshelf, a lamp, a clock, a pen, paper, a microcalculator and other necessary items are installed on the desk, as well as alarm buttons to call parents in case of need.

The level of Japanese high schools is slightly higher than the level of American high schools. As can be seen from the above, the education system in Japan has achieved a high degree of harmony both in form and content. There are many aspects worth learning from. Another important aspect is that in Japan, not only national traditions, but also advanced pedagogical work experiences of developed countries such as the USA, France, and Germany have been creatively adopted.

There is no doubt that such experiences will be useful in raising the education system of our Republic to a higher level.

The educational system of the United States of America. Secondary education in America is divided into 12 years of elementary, middle and lower schools. Most of them are public schools, and 88% of students study in them. Educational institutions are financed by state and municipal budgets. In the United States, 7.5% of the gross domestic product is spent on education every year. 12 percent of students go to private schools, their material resources are formed at the expense of parents, various funds and donations.

In countries, educational institutions do not have numbers, but they are named after regions or famous people.

Usually every classroom has a TV and a computer. Computer classrooms are connected to high speed internet. There are a lot of photocopiers in America. Because almost all tasks are given to students by the teacher in printed form. In primary school, the class teacher changes every year. The amount of mathematical knowledge in primary grades is a little lighter compared to the level of Russian and English schools. The multiplication table starts from the 3rd grade.

One of the unique methods in American schools is to keep a "Report Card" for each student. In it, the student is evaluated according to 10 different behaviors. As parents familiarize themselves with this card, they can identify their children's weaknesses and try to correct them. they try.

American pedagogues use the "Favorite Toy" method for students of 1-3 grades once a week. This method describes a children's toy. The purpose of using this method is to teach the child to get rid of shyness and to speak freely among classmates. Excessive democratization of education in America creates difficulties in checking and controlling the accuracy of student knowledge. Therefore, in a country with a rich material base and experience, there are children who are completely illiterate.

The positive application of the acceptable aspects of the educational system in the USA is of great importance.

German education system. Germany is one of the centers of world enlightenment and culture. In this country, every citizen has the right to freely develop his personality, to choose a school, place of study and profession depending on his talents and abilities.

The school education system consists of primary and secondary educational institutions. Studying in all public schools is free.

School education in Germany is divided into the following school types: primary school; vocational schools; primary school; real school; gymnasium; general school; special school.

Primary school is the foundation of the education system. After primary school, students go to secondary school. Basic or comprehensive public school is compulsory for all students who have completed primary school and have not attended real school or gymnasium. Primary school teachers feel that they are not teachers, but social pedagogues. But the students in the main school are forced to receive vocational education despite their poor mastery. Real schools belong to the second stage and usually include grades 5-10. The Real School provides high-level extended general education and prepares students for professional training courses to become holders of professions that require high demands on independent thinking, sense of responsibility, and people management skills.

German education has a very complex system in its own way. The German state has an educational system that has justified itself in taking a place among the developed countries.

French education system. The quality of education in France is controlled by the Inspectorate General for Education, Sports and Research. This general inspection works for 4 ministries. The General Inspection performs 4 tasks:

1. Support - education, science, sports, culture management offices, rectors of higher education;
2. Expertise - activities of ministries, agencies, contracts, leaders, services, structures, etc.;
3. Evaluation - organizations, institutions, structures, social and political situation, personnel;
4. Control - organizations, institutions, services and personnel.

The diversity of experiences gathered in the General Inspectorate allows for the coordination of state policies from kindergarten to doctoral studies. This affects the development of education, science and youth, the involvement of students in sports, community life and public studies.

According to the French education system, a child goes to a preparatory class at the age of 6-7, and then studies in the same school for 4 years in the primary class. These primary classes usually operate as separate primary schools and their inspections are also separate.

The next level of secondary education is called college. There, the child studies for 4 years and at the end of it, he gives a certificate as an incomplete school graduate.

For the next 3 years, he will study at lyceums of different fields and at the end of the year, he will pass the bachelor's exam and be admitted to higher education institutions depending on the result.

The school principal does not fire teachers. Teachers who do not perform well are inspected by the educational inspectorate according to the director's recommendation. His discipline, teaching activity, reputation among children and parents will be carefully studied and appropriate measures will be taken.

The demand for school teachers is very high in France. Especially in elementary schools, a teacher should be a master of his profession, an excellent speaker, an artist, a musician, an athlete, an organizer, and an exemplary character. French education systems do not provide for extracurricular institutions. However, there are various clubs in schools and lyceums.

It has been more than 2 years since the establishment of the education inspection under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Over the past period, purposeful work has been carried out to study advanced foreign experiences in performing the tasks assigned to the inspection and to introduce them to the assessment of the quality of education in our country. We are currently adapting the advanced aspects of foreign pedagogy and making it

one of the most advanced pedagogies in the world by introducing new subjects into the curriculum. [6]

Currently in US pedagogy:

1. Bringing up the child in the spirit of confidence in his own strength and potential.
2. Struggle to realize the student's smallest personal potential
3. Do not humiliate the child, do not knock down human values and pride
4. Directing the student to the profession from an early age
5. Educate with a spirit of pride and pride for the country.

In Japanese education:

1. Thoroughly prepare the child for school
2. To strengthen the responsibility of parents for the education and upbringing of children;
3. The attention paid to the physical development of students;
4. High demand for teaching staff;
5. Consistent work with young talents.

In German education:

1. Strong emphasis on progressive teaching;
2. Strengthening the labor education of students
3. Vocational guidance.

In French education:

1. Subject organization of education from pre-school education;
2. Thorough implementation of primary education in 3 stages
3. Great attention is paid to providing education with didactic tools.
4. Various firms, concerns, enterprises, strong connections and other exemplary aspects of educational institutions are moving to our education. Of course, any innovation, change, serious analyzes and experiences enter education. [7]

Uzbekistan is scheduled to participate in PISA and PIRLS international assessment system in 2021. Everyone should prepare for this test. That is, our 3rd graders this year will be 4th graders in 2021. In order to prepare students for this process, it is necessary to share the international experiences of developed countries participating in the international evaluation system.

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